

Working Instruction	WIN_SOP00_41
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Manual for publication of digital objects in Knowledge Junction

Special Requirements	<p>This Working instruction is a controlled document maintained by Quality Management. It may not be deleted without comparable controls. Please note that this document becomes uncontrolled once printed. Make sure by always referring only to the Repository that you have the right version in use.</p> <p>The update is done when there are changes in EFSA with respect to what is stated in the document (e.g., Relevant Standards, legislation and documents, change in procedure, etc.). The person responsible for the update is the Lead author with the support of the QM.</p>
Process Responsibility	<p>It is the responsibility of the relevant process owner and the relevant staff to follow these instructions. Responsibilities for performing specific steps are outlined in the document.</p>

SCOPE AND OBJECTIVES	
This work instruction describes the steps of Zenodo publication. Furthermore, provides description about Knowledge Junction community. This WIN has to be followed by scientific officers publishing digital objects. The document contains two major parts namely General and Specific Introduction	
RELEVANT STANDARDS, LEGISLATION AND DOCUMENTS	
Dublin Core Metadata Element Set ISO Standard 15836:2009 DataCite Metadata Schema Global Agricultural Concept Scheme Creative commons licenses EFSA authorship principles The EU Food Safety Almanac EFSA Strategy 2020 Knowledge Junction	
ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITION	
NA	NA
INSTRUCTIONS	

About Knowledge Junction

The Knowledge Junction is a curated community in the Zenodo repository for research sharing. Zenodo is an open source product, built on the foundation of the CERN Invenio digital library. It is used by the OpenAIRE project, and was commissioned by the EC to support their nascent Open Data Policy by providing a catch-all repository for EC funded research. This community enables the exchange of evidence and supporting materials used in food and feed safety risk assessments, with the goal of improving transparency, reproducibility and evidence reuse. Submissions of evidence (reports, datasets, images, videos, laboratory outputs, etc.) and supporting materials generated during risk assessment (software, tools, models, code, protocols, appraisal schemes, FAQs etc.) in all file formats are welcome from any registered user of Zenodo. Member State organisations, EEA/EFTA countries and Pre-Accession countries are encouraged to upload, through national

representatives, all information relevant to risk assessment activities including risk assessment mandates, outputs (opinions, reports, statements, guidance documents), national workplans related to risk assessment, relevant technical reports, any other relevant document, data and software.

Each submission is assigned a unique and persistent digital object identifier (DOI) that allows easy retrieval and persistence of published items. Each publication requires metadata acknowledging authors and contributors and has a license specifying the conditions of use. In this way the reuse of any object deposited can be tracked by the provider. The community is intended for uploading digital files that have not been published elsewhere with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). However, if the material is not subject to copyright restrictions, the file can be uploaded into the community and the existing DOI should be used. All content submitted is viewed by the community curator for acceptance and publication and high quality metadata is essential. The content of this repository can be used by EFSA's Panels and Working Groups and any other interested parties when preparing new risk assessments. The Knowledge Junction enables broad dissemination of evidence, collaboration between countries and national organisations, avoids duplication of activities and increases visibility of countries' activities in the area of food and feed safety risk assessment. The platform is extremely user-friendly and intuitive with an advanced end-user interface and is visually appealing. The following screenshots will guide you through the process of registration in the Platform and publication of digital objects in the community.

I. General Instructions

Introduction

Zenodo is an online publication platform for research outputs and it works with communities, where users can opt to add their publication. Communities are curated, which means the curator will assess if a publication meets the specific requirements for a community and either approves or rejects its listing within the community. The curator does not review the content of the record hence, the responsibility for publication of the record lies with the authors.

Account

To log into [Zenodo](#), an account is required. You can quickly create your own account. Some of EFSA's units have a shared account linked to their functional mailbox, so all publications are under one Zenodo account. If you already have a GitHub or ORCID account, you can link those as well. Please note that if you need to make edits or new versions of an existing upload, the account that was used to originally create the upload must be used.

zenodo

Log in to account

Sign in with ORCID

Sign in with GitHub

Sign in with OpenAIRE

OR

Email Address

Password

Log in

New to Zenodo? Sign up

Privacy notice

Header Buttons functions

Once logged in with your account, you can view your uploads, edit them, or create new uploads.

- 1 This button redirects to communities' page which allows searching for specific communities.
- 2 The dashboard provides access to your content in Zenodo - to your uploads, communities and requests.
- 3 Requests inbox button allows the quick access to view your pending requests such as draft reviews, community inclusion, ownerships transfers, file replacements etc.
- 4 Quick actions menu allows to quickly create new uploads or new communities.

Create a new upload

To create a new upload, click the plus icon (4) in the header, and select New upload from the drop-down menu.

A new deposit form where the user can upload files, add metadata, set restrictions and save/publish an upload, is created in order to create a new upload.

community Selection
Add the community Knowledge Junction mandatorily, by inserting in the search field 'Knowledge AND Junction' to find it, the select it to add it to the record. Please keep in mind that names of the communities are case sensitive.

Add/Remove files

Click the Upload files button or drag and drop one or more files onto the drop zone to start uploading files. By default, you can upload maximum up to 100 files and a total of 50GB.

A file can be removed by clicking on the trashcan icon from the right-hand side.

Metadata fill in

Fill in the minimal required metadata fields under Basic information. The fields are marked with a small red star.

A more detailed guide to all fields in the form can be found when referring to [describe records](#) and to the chapters below.

Digital Object Identifier (DOI)

If there is already a DOI for the upload. Answer "yes" to the question and copy/paste the existing DOI. Note, make sure the existing DOI is for the same object. For instance, if you upload a supporting dataset to a journal article, you should NOT use the journal article DOI. If there is not a DOI for the upload. If the upload does not have a DOI, answer "no" to the question. The "Get a DOI now!" button allows you to reserve a DOI, so you can include it into the files you upload if so desired (e.g. to include the DOI into a PDF). ATTENTION: If you delete the draft upload, the reserved DOI will be lost.

The DOI will only be registered once the record is published.

When creating a new version of the upload, a new DOI for that newly added version will be needed/requested. However, the overarching DOI number will not change and will always redirect to the latest version added.

Resource type

Select the type of resource that was uploaded (e.g publication, dataset, software, poster, presentation). For mixed type uploads, the type which best reflects the nature of the upload should be chosen.

A screenshot of a web form showing a dropdown menu labeled "Resource type" with a red asterisk. The menu is open, and the word "Dataset" is selected and displayed in the input field.

Title

A clear and informative title for should be provided for the upload.

A screenshot of a web form showing an input field labeled "Title" with a red asterisk. Below the input field is a button with a plus sign and the text "Add titles".

Publication date

The publication date is when an upload was first published (made available to a public audience). By default, the publication date is set to the date the draft upload was created. This date can be changed in the draft upload before publication.

A screenshot of a web form showing an input field labeled "Publication date" with a red asterisk. The date "2023-08-28" is entered in the field. Below the input field is a small text note: "In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of the first publication. Format: YYYY-MM-DD, YYYY-MM, or YYYY. For intervals use DATE/DATE, e.g. 1939/1945."

Creators (Authors)

Click the "Add creator" button to add one or more creators/authors of the record. Creators appear in the citation string of an upload. A creator can be a person or organisation. There is the option to search for creators (based on [ORCID](#) profiles for persons and [ROR](#) registry for organisations), or the contributors' information can be added manually. One or more affiliations can be added and role can be selected from the drop-down menu for a creator.

Add creator

Person Organization

Search for persons by name, identifier, or affiliation...

Search for persons by name, identifier, or affiliation...

Family name Given names

Name identifiers

e.g. ORCID, ISNI or GND.

Affiliations

Search or create affiliation'

Role

Select role

Description

Provide a description of the upload.

 Description

Paragraph **B** *I*

Languages

When you start typing the language, you should wait for a few moments until the language pops up from a pre-filled list and can be selected.

 Languages

Search for a language by name (e.g "eng", "fr" or "Polish")

Keywords and subjects

To insert keywords/subjects, type a keyword/subject in the 'Search for a subject by name' box and then click 'Add'.

 Keywords and subjects

Suggest from

Add EFSA

Additional notes

To add notes, click on the 'Add description' button and select 'Notes' from the drop-down menu under 'Type'.

This field needs to contain the country code (or EU), language code, file type, and contact email. The elements are separated by a semicolon, e.g.: "EU; en; xlsx; contact@email.com". This is important as this field is used to extract statistics on Zenodo by EFSA and is therefore also mandatory to be provided in this format.

Related works

This field helps to link the current upload to other resources which are already published. The relationship of the upload with the existing publication can be defined by selecting the appropriate options from the drop-down menu of the 'Relation', 'Identifier', 'Scheme' and 'Resource type' fields. Most frequently a DOI is used as an identifier. The DOI option is selected from the drop-down menu of the 'Scheme'.

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, IISTC, URNs, and URLs.

Related works

License

License type is usually Creative Commons 4.0. Knowledge Junction content is usually Open Access, i.e., once published the upload is available to all users.

Set Visibility

The visibility of the files in the record once published can be set using the options available (note, the metadata is always publicly accessible):

The visibility can be set as 'Public' or 'Restricted' for the files. If the files visibility is restricted, an embargo date can be set at a later date and the record can be shared with specific users.

Visibility*

Files only

Public Restricted

Public

The record and files are publicly accessible.

Options

Apply an embargo ⓘ
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Apply an embargo

The visibility must be set to 'Restricted' to be able to apply an embargo. The box 'Apply an embargo' must be ticked and then an 'Embargo until' date must be provided as well. The files will automatically be made publicly available on the chosen date at midnight UTC. Optionally, a reason for applying the embargo can be provided.

Options

Apply an embargo ⓘ
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Embargo until*

YYYY-MM-DD

Format: YYYY-MM-DD

Embargo reason

Optionally, describe the reason for the embargo.

Mandatory items

Mandatory items for uploads to be accepted by the EFSA curator are title, date, community, upload type, keywords, and additional notes. Other fields in the upload view are optional, depending on each upload and its information.

IMPORTANT:

adding a new version of the file uploaded creates a new DOI number of that version. Editing information in the upload does not create a new version.

If you added a wrong file and published it, to have it removed you should contact Zenodo support via <https://zenodo.org/support> and follow the instructions received.

Publication

The option 'Save draft' can be used to save the upload and validate the entered data. Once saved, the browser window can be closed, and the upload can be completed later. Instructions on how to find an upload again. can be found on the manage records section. The 'Preview' button allows to see how the record will look like once published. Note: the minimal required metadata must be provided, to be able to preview the record. In case of errors or missing fields an error message will be displayed at the top of the screen. When all data is inserted correctly, all files are attached and the record can be published, press 'Submit for review'. This will send the record to the curator.

The screenshot shows a 'Draft' interface with the following elements:

- Buttons: 'Save draft', 'Preview', and a large blue 'Submit for review' button.
- Section: 'Visibility' with a dropdown menu showing 'Public' (selected) and 'Restricted'.
- Message: A green box with a lock icon stating 'Public. The record and files are publicly accessible.'
- Section: 'Options' with a checkbox for 'Apply an embargo' and a note: 'Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.'
- Button: A red 'Delete' button at the bottom.

After sending for review, you will be prompted to read and check Zenodo prompts, and to insert a message, which is optional. In case you submit the record from a generic/unit email, it would be advisable to send a message and insert your name, so that the curator may contact you immediately in case needed.

The 'Submit for review' dialog box contains the following elements:

- Section: 'Submit for review' with a warning icon and text: 'Before requesting review, please read and check the following:'
- Checkboxes:
 - The 'Knowledge Junction' curators will have access to view and edit your upload's metadata and files.
 - If your upload is accepted by the community curators, it will be immediately published. Before that, you will still be able to modify metadata and files of this upload.
- Text: 'Message to curators (optional)' above a text input field.
- Buttons: 'Cancel' and a large blue 'Submit record for review' button.

The curator receives an email to 'accept' (or 'reject') the upload. You will be contacted at the email address of the account used to create the upload or at the one inserted in the additional notes, in case we need more information related to your upload.

If you need edit an existing record, i.e. no change in the files attached, always 'Save draft' first before publishing. Everything that is saved is listed as a draft record before it is published.

In this case the curator will not get an email to curate as the record had been previously accepted.

IMPORTANT:

Once published the record is publicly available, even before curator approval. The curator's role is only to accept the publication to be listed in the Knowledge Junction, not the approval of the actual publication itself.

There is a one-month grace period for file modification and replacement, after the publication. To proceed with it, a request needs to be sent to info@zenodo.org. Files cannot be removed or replaced after the grace period. After re-publication you can only create new versions of the record (old versions always remain available).

Support

If you have any questions regarding a publication and need help or clarifications, you can internally contact the EFSA curator: curator.KnowledgeJunction@efsa.europa.eu. You can also obtain support directly from Zenodo if you need help with your account or the platform:

- info@zenodo.org
- <https://zenodo.org/support>

For more detailed guidance on navigating Zenodo, new uploads, communities, etc, please visit Zenodo [Docs](#).